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№ 5

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Elektron nashr,
84 sahifa, dekabr, 2024-yil.

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil
28-avgustdagi 360/5-son
qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar
asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy
ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

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MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS OF THE PROCESS OF PHYSICS-CHEMICAL HYDRODYNAMICS

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Abstract: In this article, mathematical models of physical-chemical hydrodynamic processes suitable for mineral mixing, which is one of the geo-technological methods used in the extraction of minerals, were systematically analyzed. Compatible with these models, although there is little opportunity to find analytical solutions of the differential equation, these processes were studied because of its high efficiency and closeness to the exact solution. Analytical solutions corresponding to the obtained results were recommended.

Keywords: physical-chemical processes, useful component, mathematical model, concentration quantity, optimization factors, Fourier integral, formula of cosines, analytical solutions, numerical-approximate methods.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada tog'-kon sanoatida qo'llaniladigan geotexnologik usullardan biri bo'lgan minerallarni aralashtirish uchun mos bo'lgan fizik-kimyoviy gidrodinamik jarayonlarning matematik modellari tizimli tahlil qilindi. Ushbu modellarga mos keladigan bo'lsa-da, differensial tenglamaning analitik echimlarini topish qiyin bo'lsa-da, bu jarayonlar yuqori samaradorligi va aniq yechimga yaqinligi tufayli o'rganilgan. Natijalarga mos keladigan analitik echimlar tavsiya etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: fizik-kimyoviy jarayonlar, foydali komponent, matematik model, konsentratsiya miqdori, optimallashtirish omillari, Furye integrali, kosinuslar formulasi, analitik yechimlar, sonli-taqribiy usullar.

Аннотация: В данной статье были систематически проанализированы математические модели физико-химических гидродинамических процессов, пригодных для смешивания минералов, что является одним из геотехнологических методов, используемых при добыче полезных ископаемых. Совместимые с этими моделями, хотя и маловероятно найти аналитические решения дифференциального уравнения, эти процессы были изучены из-за его высокой эффективности и близости к точному решению. Были рекомендованы аналитические решения, соответствующие полученным результатам.

Ключевые слова: physical-chemical processes, useful component, mathematical model, concentration quantity, optimization factors, Fourier integral, formula of cosines, analytical solutions, numerical-approximate methods.

INTRODUCTION

It is natural that the deterioration of the quality of minerals and the natural weakening of the land will lead to a rapid increase in the demand for their rational use and scientific research in the field of mineral enrichment. The complexity of the problem has led to the emergence of narrower scientific research and the inclusion of several disciplines in the field of mountain geology. They are such sciences as mathematics, mechanics, cybernetics, physics, physics-chemistry, radiation processes, microbiology.

In this regard, it is appropriate to emphasize the following tasks that must be solved:

- development of geologic-genetic models of useful component deposits and ore fields to create scientific bases for searching and forecasting high-grade ore concentrations;

- to create large-scale prediction maps in order to distinguish regions of promising mineral raw materials;

-creating a mathematical model of the production of ore deposits and making their software packages suitable for modern computers.

The models of these processes are simultaneously represented by a system of equations of hydrodynamics, diffusion and kinetics of substance exchange. By solving the underground mixing equations, it is possible to determine the amount of product in the ore-conducting boundary layer, the nature of mixing, and the consumption of product in the internal parts. There are various methods of solving the equation, which can be divided into analytical and numerical-approximate methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The essence of the underground leaching method lies in bringing minerals into a mobile state by forming thermal, mass-exchange, chemical, diffusion and hydrodynamic processes at the site of their occurrence. Many researchers have made significant contributions to the development of these issues, including foreign researchers V.Zh. Ahrens, V.G. Bakhurov, N.P. Buslenko, N.N. Verigin, L.G. Voroshnin, V.S. Golubev, V.A. Grabovnikov, A.N. Kanavalov, L. Lukner, V.M. Shestakov, I.K. Lutsenko, V.I. Beletsky, V.A. Mamilov, V.N. Nikolaevsky, G.Kh. Khcheyan, I.S. Naftulin, I.A. Charny, E.I. Rogov, V.G. Yazikov, M.V. Shumilin, as well as Uzbek scientists such as academicians V.K. Kabulov, V.R. Rakhimov, B.F. Abutaliev, professors N.M. Mukhidinov, H. Karimov, I. Alimov, T. Valiev and others [1-10].

They considered the physical and mathematical foundations of geotechnological processes of mineral extraction, compiled the main equations and methods of engineering calculation of thermal, filtration and other problems of underground smelting, dissolution and leaching processes, and formulated control problems for various geotechnological methods [11-15].

Analysis of models and computational algorithms for technological processes of underground smelting developed to date shows that there are still many unsolved problems.

Based on this, in this dissertation special attention is paid to the problem of developing models for controlling the underground smelting process for phenomena occurring in a heterogeneous environment, taking into account the real properties of the object, as well as making appropriate decisions and forecasting using the developed models [16-20].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The analytical solution is important because it has no error except for the error present in the finite-difference approximation. All existing solutions are valid for some cases and differ from each other for different physical processes. It follows from the complexity of the mathematical model that it is not possible to obtain an analytical solution without any simplifications.

In the same sense, the diffusion equation also has an analytical solution only in some cases. To obtain analytical solutions, various mathematical methods are used, for example, Green's function method, Laplace or Fourie substitutions.

Suppose the one-dimensional convective diffusion problem is expressed as follows [2].

$$C_t + UC_x = KC_{xx} \quad (1)$$

let the equation be given by the initial and boundary conditions $c(t=0) = 0$, $c(x=0) = c(x=\infty) = 0$. Here, when K and U consist of constant coefficients, it is possible to create analytical solutions of a much simpler form for the given problem. It is known that the solution was found using the Fure substitution

$$C(x, t) = \hat{O}(x, t) e^{\alpha - b} \quad (2)$$

is searched for in view [1]. Here, a and b are currently unknown coefficients, and to find their expression, we take special derivatives from equation (2) with respect to x and t:

$$\begin{aligned} C_x &= \hat{O}_x e^{\alpha-b} + \hat{O} a e^{\alpha-b}; \\ \tilde{N}_{xx} &= \hat{O}_{xx} e^{\alpha-b} + 2\hat{O}_x a e^{\alpha-b} + \hat{O}_x a^2 e^{\alpha-b}; \\ C_t &= \hat{O}_t e^{\alpha-b} - b\hat{O} e^{\alpha-b}. \end{aligned}$$

We put the expression of the special derivatives into the equation in problem (1), for convenience we write e in the form without temporary degrees:

$$\hat{O}_t e - b\hat{O} e + U\hat{O}_x e + Ua\hat{O} = K(\hat{O}_{xx} e + 2a\hat{O}_x e + a^2 \hat{O} e).$$

We group the resulting expression with respect to the function Φ :

$$\hat{O}_t = K\hat{O}_{xx} + (2Ka - U)\hat{O}_x + (Ka^2 - Ua + b)\hat{O}$$

To convert the generated expression into a homogeneous parabolic type equation and to find the value of unknowns a and b, we set the coefficients in front of Φ_x and Φ to 0.

Then $2Ka - U = 0$ is equal to $a = \frac{U}{2K}$.

On the other hand, if we consider $Ka^2 - Ua + b = 0$, from $K\frac{U^2}{4K^2} - U\frac{U}{2K} + b = 0$ this expression $b = \frac{U^2}{4K}$ comes out.

We put the values of the coefficients a and b found in equation (2):

$$\hat{O}(x, t) = C(x, t) e^{-\frac{U}{2K}x - \frac{U^2}{4K}t} \quad (3)$$

In that case,

$$\hat{O}_t = K\hat{O}_{xx} \quad (4)$$

Equation's solution will be the formula 3.

$$C(x, 0) = f(x)$$

For this case, the solution of equation (4) when the initial distribution occurs is as follows.

$$\hat{O}(x, 0) = f(x) e^{-\frac{U}{2K}x} \quad (5)$$

Now we look for a general solution to equation (4).

For this, the function $\Phi(x, t)$. We will write as follows

$$\hat{O}(x, t) = X(x)T(t)$$

In that case the equation $X' = K''T$ or $\frac{T'}{K} = \frac{X''}{X} = -\lambda^2$ will be formed.

Since each ratio depends on and is equal to different variables, they must necessarily be equal to some constant.

We create two equations from it and solve each one separately.

$$1) T' + \lambda^2 K = 0, \quad \frac{dT}{dt} = -\lambda^2 K, \quad \frac{dT}{T} = -\lambda^2 K dt, \quad \ln T = -\lambda^2 K t + c, \quad T = c e^{-\lambda^2 K t}$$

2) $X'' + X\lambda^2 = 0$ since the equation is a linear differential equation, its solution will be as follows
 $X = A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x$

Then Φ is a function which will be expressed

$$\hat{O}_\lambda = e^{-k\lambda^2 t} (A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x)$$

Here C is included in the constants $A(\lambda)$ $B(\lambda)$.

Since A and B have different values at different values of the argument, we express the solution of the linear differential equation in summation form.

$$\sum_\lambda e^{-k\lambda^2 t} (A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x) d\lambda$$

The sum, in turn, is expressed as an integral from 0 to infinity:

$$\hat{O}(x, t) = \int_0^\infty e^{-k\lambda^2 t} (A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x) d\lambda \quad (6)$$

(5) according to the initial condition:

$$\hat{O}(x, 0) = f(x) e^{-\frac{U}{2K} x}$$

$$\hat{O}(x, 0) = \int_0^\infty (A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x) d\lambda$$

(6) according to

If we find $f(x)$ from equation (5) and replace F with the above value, we can see that it is equal to
 $f(x) = \int_0^\infty (A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x) e^{\frac{U}{2K} x} d\lambda$

Here we assume that the function $f(x)$ is represented by the Fourier integral, i.e

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left(\int_{-\infty}^\infty f(\xi) \cos \lambda(\xi - x) d\xi \right) e^{\frac{U\xi}{2K}} d\lambda \quad (7)$$

Or if we use the formula of the cosine of the sum:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left(\int_{-\infty}^\infty f(\xi) \cos \xi d\xi \right) \cos \lambda x + \left(\int_{-\infty}^\infty f(\xi) \sin \xi d\xi \right) \sin \lambda x e^{\frac{U\xi}{2K}} d\lambda \quad (8)$$

Comparing formulas (7) and (8).

$$A(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty f(\xi) \cos \xi d\xi$$

$$B(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty f(\xi) \sin \xi d\xi \quad (9)$$

Putting the values of (9) into expression (6), we make the necessary substitutions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{O}(x,t) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) \cos \xi \, d\xi \cos \lambda x + \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) \sin \xi \, d\xi \right) \sin \lambda x \right] e^{\frac{U\xi}{2k}} d\lambda = \\
 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) (\cos \xi \cos \lambda x + \sin \xi \sin \lambda x) d\xi \right] e^{\frac{U\xi}{2k}} d\lambda = \\
 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) \cos \lambda(\xi - x) d\xi \right) e^{\frac{U\xi}{2k}} d\lambda
 \end{aligned}$$

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

By changing the sign of the integral, we create the resulting formula:

$$\hat{O}(x,t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[f(\xi) \int_0^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \cos \lambda(\xi - x) d\lambda \right] e^{\frac{U\xi}{2k}} d\xi \quad (10)$$

Now we calculate the integral expression in small brackets.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \cos \lambda(\xi - x) d\lambda = \left[z = \lambda\sqrt{k}, \, d = \sqrt{k} d\lambda, \, \beta = \frac{\xi - x}{\sqrt{k}} \right] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-z^2} \cos \beta z dz \quad (11)$$

We define the integral expression:

$$p(\beta) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-z^2} \cos \beta z dz \quad (12)$$

and we differentiate:

$$p'(\beta) = - \int_0^{\infty} e^{-z^2} z \sin \beta z dz$$

we use the method of integration by pieces:

$$u = \sin \beta z, \quad d = \beta \cos \beta z \, dz, \quad du = \beta \cos \beta z \, dz, \quad v = \frac{1}{2} e^{-z^2}$$

In that case,

$$p'(\beta) = \frac{1}{2} (e^{-z^2} \sin \beta z) \Big|_0^{\infty} - \frac{\beta}{2} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-z^2} \cos \beta z dz$$

The first addendum in the expression is equal to zero when setting the threshold values, and if we replace the second addendum with the expression from the original definition

$$p'(\beta) = - \frac{\beta}{2} p(\beta)$$

only the expression remains. We solve the resulting ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{dp}{d\beta} = - \frac{\beta}{2} p;$$

$$\frac{dp}{p} = - \frac{\beta}{2} d\beta$$

Integrating both sides:

$$h \quad p = -\frac{\beta^2}{4} + c, \quad p = e^{-\frac{\beta^2}{4}} \quad (13)$$

Now we determine the value of the constant C. (12) from the formula

$$p(0) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-z^2} dz = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$$

and from (13) $p(0) = c = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$ is obtained. So, according to formula (13), we can write the solution as follows:

$$p(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} e^{-\frac{\beta^2}{4}} \quad (14)$$

We put the expression (14) into (11):

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-k\lambda^2 t} \cos \lambda(\xi - x) d\lambda = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} e^{-\frac{\beta^2}{4}} = \left[\beta = \frac{\xi - x}{\sqrt{k}} \right] = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{t}} e^{-\frac{(\xi-x)^2}{4k}}$$

And finally, if we put the generated expression into the formula (10), the solution of the differential equation (4) is obtained:

$$\hat{O}(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{k\pi t}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) e^{-\frac{(\xi-x)^2}{4k} + \frac{U\xi}{2k}} d\xi \quad (15)$$

Then the value of $C(x, t)$ in expression (3) is equal to the following.

So, the solution for problem (1) is found using Fourier transformation formula.

$$C(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi K}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-\xi-U)^2}{4K}} f(\xi) d\xi \quad (16)$$

will appear. Suppose that the field under consideration is bounded and satisfies the following conditions. Let $f(x)=1$ if the domain $|x| \leq g$ is bounded by g , and $f(x)=0$ if the domain g is outside the domain $|x| \geq g$. Then expression (16)

$$C(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi K}} \int_{-g}^g e^{-\frac{(\xi-y)^2}{4Kt}} d\xi \quad (17)$$

appears [3]. Marking is used here $y = x - U$. To make the integral expression more precise, we

replace it with variable assignment $z = \frac{\xi - y}{2\sqrt{K}}$.

Since the value of the integral of the probability exactly corresponds to the values under the integral and on the boundary of the integral in the expression we created, we can write the solution in the following form:

$$C(x, t) = \frac{g}{2} \left(\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{g-y}{2\sqrt{Kt}} \right) + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{g+y}{2\sqrt{Kt}} \right) \right) \quad (18)$$

taking into account the definition $\operatorname{erfc}(z) = 1 - \operatorname{erf}(z)$, we can express the solution of the given problem in another way:

$$C(x, t) = \frac{g}{2} \left(\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x-y}{2\sqrt{Kt}} \right) + \exp \left(\frac{x^2}{K} \right) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x+y}{2\sqrt{Kt}} \right) \right) \quad (19)$$

Fields of application of the obtained results. It is known that any practical problem does not always have analytical solutions. Most analytical solutions are obtained only for special cases. In practical processes, all indicators are objective. For example, the area under consideration may be infinite, and the coefficients involved in the equation may be variable rather than constant. In general, since it is very rare to find the solutions of all differential equations using an analytical method, in practice they are often approximated using numerical methods. Based on this, we come to the conclusion that it is necessary to find and apply numerical calculation methods that lead to effective results in order to solve any practical problem.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, in this work, various methods of solving the equations representing the process and their possibilities are analyzed, specific advantages of approximate-analytical solutions and certain limitations imposed on them are presented. The approximate-analytical solution of the convective diffusion equation was derived using different substitutions: Laplace, Fourier, and Green substitutions, assuming a flat and constant filtration rate. Approximate-analytical solutions for the values corresponding to the estimated object were obtained on the basis of the working algorithms according to the Bubnov-Galerkin method, and parallel lines corresponding to the results were drawn, and the physico-chemical properties of the process were systematically analyzed. From the obtained results, it is possible to make such decisions that the models selected for the EQ process correspond to its physical characteristics and they provide the opportunity to obtain the necessary information in the appropriate control process. For this, it is necessary to develop computational algorithms for solving this two-dimensional mathematical model in all cases. Therefore, the problem of creating efficient algorithms suitable for the proposed mathematical model is considered based on numerical-approximate methods. There are several finite-difference schemes for solving equations representing hydrodynamic processes by numerical calculation methods, and when it is necessary to choose the most effective method from them, the obtained results and the analytical method it will be possible to compare the results obtained with As a result, it is possible to solve the set model in the most optimal way.

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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 5

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

